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Kurbanov Ravshanbek Davlatovich

*O'zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar akademiyasining akademigi, tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, Respublika ixtisoslashtirilgan kardiologiya ilmiy-amaliy tibbiyot markazining direktor maslahatchisi (Toshkent)
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Pokushalov Evgeniy Anatolevich

tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, "Yangi tibbiy texnologiyalar markazi" (YTTM) klinik tarmog'ining ilmiy ishlar va rivojlanish bo'yicha bosh direktorining o'rinbosari (Novosibirsk) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2560-5167>

Zufarov Mirjamol Mirumarovich

tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, "akad V. Vohidov nomidagi RIJM davlat muassasasi" bo'limi boshlig'i" <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4822-3193>

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tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, Tibbiyot xodimlarining kasbiy malakasini oshirish markazi direktori (Toshkent)

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Jan Kovak

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*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Head of the Department of Internal Diseases No. 2 of the Samarkand State Medical University, Chairman of the Association of Physicians of the Samarkand Region.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5705-4972>*

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<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2560-5167>*

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*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Head of the Department of the State Institution "RSNPMTSH named after acad. V. Vakhidov"
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Alimov Doniyor Anvarovich
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tibbiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent,
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<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2679-1296>

Alimov Doniyor Anvarovich
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PhD, Director of Samarkand branch of
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Practical Medical Center for Therapy and
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<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1766-4458>

Agababyan Irina Rubenovna
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Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
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of medical workers

Khusinova Shoira Akbarovna
PhD, Associate Professor, Head of the
Department of General Practice,
Family Medicine FAGE of the
Samarkand State Medical Institute

Shodikulova Gulandom Zikriyaevna
Doctor of Medical Sciences, professor,
head of the Department of Internal
Diseases N 3 of Samarkand state medical
institute (Samarkand)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2679-1296>

Халиков Каххор Мирзаевич
кандидат медицинских наук, доцент
заведующий кафедрой биологической
химии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского
университета

Аннаев Музаффар
Ассистент кафедры внутренних
болезней и кардиологии №2
Самаркандского государственного
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(технический секретарь)

Тулабаева Гавхар Миракбаровна
Заведующая кафедрой кардиологии,
Центр развития профессиональной
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**Абдумаджидов Хамидулла
Амануллаевич**
Бухарский государственный
медицинский институт имени Абу
Али ибн Сино. Кафедра «Хирургические
болезни и реанимация». Доктор
медицинских наук, профессор.

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к.м.н., директор Самаркандского
областного отделения
Республиканского специализированного
научно-практического медицинского
центра кардиологии (г. Самарканд)

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PhD, ассистент кафедры внутренних
болезней №2 Самаркандского
Государственного Медицинского
университета (ответственный
секретарь)

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Tibbiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti
Biologik kimyo kafedrasini mudiri

Annayev Muzaffar G'iyos o'g'li
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti 2-son
ichki kasalliklar va kardiologiya kafedrasini
assistenti (texnik kotib)

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kardiologiya kafedrasini mudiri, tibbiyot
xodimlarining kasbiy malakasini rivojlantirish
markazi, tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abdumadjidov Xamidulla Amanullayevich
«Abu Ali ibn Sino nomidagi Buxoro davlat
tibbiyot oliygohi» Xirurgiya kasalliklari va
reanimatsiya kafedrasini professori, tibbiyot
fanlari doktori.

Saidov Maqsud Arifovich
tibbiyot fanlari nomzodi,
Respublika ixtisoslashgan kardialogiya
ilmiy amaliy tibbiyot markazi Samarqand
viloyat mintaqaviy filiali direktori
(Samarqand)

Nasirova Zarina Akbarovna
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot instituti
2-sonli ichki kasalliklar kafedrasini
assistenti, PhD (mas'ul kotib)

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Candidate of Medical Sciences,
Associate Professor, Head of the Department
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Medical University

Annaev Muzaffar
Assistant of the Department of Internal
Diseases and Cardiology No. 2 of the
Samarkand State Medical University
(technical secretary)

Tulabayeva Gavxar Mirakbarovna
Head of the Department of Cardiology,
Development Center professional
qualification of medical workers,
MD, professor

**Abdumadjidov Khamidulla
Amanullayevich**
"Bukhara state medical institute named
after Abu Ali ibn Sino". DSc, professor.

Saidov Maksud Arifovich
Candidate of Medical Sciences, Director
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the Republican Specialized Scientific and
Practical Medical Center of Cardiology
(Samarkand)

Nasyrova Zarina Akbarovna
PhD, Assistant of the Department of Internal
Diseases No. 2 of the Samarkand State
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Исмаилов Жамшид АбдураимовичPhD, заведующий кафедрой
внутренних болезней №4Самаркандский Государственный
медицинский университет
Самарканд, Узбекистан**Расули Фариди Орифовна**Ассистент кафедры внутренних болезней №4
Самаркандский Государственный
медицинский университет
Самарканд, Узбекистан**Тураев Хикматилла Негматович**Самаркандский Государственный
медицинский университет
Самарканд, Узбекистан

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ СВОЕВРЕМЕННОЙ ГОСПИТАЛИЗАЦИИ БОЛЬНЫХ С ОСТРЫМ ИНФАРКТОМ МИОКАРДА

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье Самаркандским филиалом Республиканского научного центра скорой медицинской помощи проведено клиническое исследование больных с диагнозом острый инфаркт миокарда в первые 12 часов и госпитализированных через 12 часов после установления диагноза инфаркт миокарда. В ходе работы были проведены сравнительные анализы по результатам лабораторных и инструментальных исследований в стадиях заболевания. Эффективность и выживаемость больных, поступивших в отделение неотложной помощи при сочетании медикаментозной и тромболитической терапии у больных, своевременно и поздно поступивших в стационар, вновь оказались высокими.

Ключевые слова: инфаркт миокарда, острый коронарный синдром, острая сердечная недостаточность, ЭКГ, ЭхоКГ, своевременная госпитализация, тромболитическая терапия.

Ismailov Jamshid AbduraimovichPh.D Head of Department of Internal Medicine No. 4
Samarkand State Medical University
Samarkand, Uzbekistan**Rasuli Farida Orifovna**Assistant of Department of Internal Medicine No. 4
Samarkand State Medical University
Samarkand, Uzbekistan**Turaev Hikmatilla Negmatovich**Samarkand State Medical University
Samarkand, Uzbekistan

EFFICIENCY OF TIMELY HOSPITALIZATION OF PATIENTS WITH ACUTE MYOCARDIAL INFRACTION

ANNOTATION

In this article, the Samarkand branch of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medicine conducted a clinical study of patients diagnosed with acute myocardial infarction in the first 12 hours and hospitalized 12 hours after the diagnosis of Myocardial Infarction. In the course of the work, comparative analysis was carried out based on the results of laboratory and instrumental studies in the stages of the disease. The efficacy and survival of patients admitted to the emergency department with a combination of drug and thrombolytic therapy in patients who were admitted to the hospital on time and delayed were turned out to be high.

Keywords: Myocardial Infarction, Acute Coronary Syndrome, Acute Heart Failure, ECG, Echocardiography, timely hospitalization, Thrombolytic Therapy.

Ismailov Jamshid Abduraimovich
PhD, Samarqand Davlat Tibbiyot Universiteti
Samarqand, O'zbekiston

Rasili Farida Orifovna
Samarqand Davlat Tibbiyot Universiteti
4-son ichki kasalliklar kafedrası assistenti
Samarqand, O'zbekiston

Turaev Hikmatilla Negmatovich
Samarqand Davlat Tibbiyot Universiteti
Samarqand, O'zbekiston

MIOKARD INFARKTI ANIQLANGAN BEMORLARNI ERTA GOSPITALIZATSIYA QILISHNING SAMARADORLIGI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada Respublika shoshilinch tibbiy yordam ilmiy markazi Samarqand filialiga o'tkir miokard infarkti tashxisi dastlabgi 12 soat ichida aniqlanib o'z vaqtida kasalxonaga yotqazilgan bemorlar hamda 35 nafar miokard infarkti aniqlangandan 12 soatdan keyin gospitalizatsiya qilingan bemorlar ustida klinik tadqiqot olib borildi. Ish jarayonida kasallikning bosqichlarida laborator hamda instrumental tekshirishlarning natijalari ustida solishtirma tahlillar olib borildi. O'z vaqtida va kechikib shifoxonaga yotkazilgan bemorlarda medikamentoz hamda torombolitik davolash natijalari bilan birgalikda shoshilinch gospitalizatsiya qilingan bemorlarda terapiyaning samaradorligi va omon qolish imkoniyati yuqori ekanligi yana bir bor aniqlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: miokard infarkti, o'tkir koronar sindrom, o'tkir yurak yetishmovchiligi, EKG, ExoKG, o'z vaqtida kasalxonaga yotqazish, trombolitik terapiya.

Introduction: Currently, in our escalating modern society, we are facing many challenges that need to be solved. In everyday life, we can face many stressful situations [3,5,9]. Psych-emotional factors are present in the lives of people regardless of any age and can lead to the development of non-communicable diseases [1,5,7]. Cardiovascular diseases, including angina pectoris, myocardial infarction (MI), unfortunately, they are more common in our modern society, according to the results of long-term observations [4,6]. Unfavorable environmental conditions and atmospheric air pollution with harmful industrial waste, as well as low mobility can cause an increase in cardiovascular disease among the population [2,10,11].

The Purpose of the Study: To study early and late complications of acute myocardial infarction depending upon on the quality of diagnosis and treatment in the SBREMC

Materials and Methods of Research: The research was carried out in the departments of the first and second therapy of the Samarkand branch of the Republican Scientific Center of Emergency Medical Care. Based on the purpose of the study, the history of patients, the age of patients in the medical history, the examination was carried out in two comparative groups. The first basic group of 35 families includes patients hospitalized within the first 6 hours after the detection of myocardial infarction of them: women-15 (42.9%), men-20 (57.1%). The second group included 35 patients who had suffered a myocardial infarction more than 6 hours ago after diagnosing, in which 11 (31.4%) women and 24 (68.6%) men.

The diagnosis of myocardial infarction in patients with complaints was made based on anamnesis, clinical examination, laboratory and instrumental examination using diagnostic methods. Diagnosis of myocardial infarction, stages of myocardial infarction and ECG symptoms were determined using established time intervals of the disease and laboratory parameters. Diagnosis and treatment of patients with MI are map out in accordance with international standards for the diagnosis and treatment of patients with MI. The examined patients were divided into the main group (OG) and the control group (KG).

The first main group of 35 families includes patients hospitalized within the first 6 hours after the detection of myocardial infarction of them: women-15 (42.9%), men-20 (57.1%). The second group included 35 patients who had suffered a myocardial infarction more than 6 hours after diagnosing, with 11 (31.4%) women and 24 (68.6%) men. From 2019 to 2022, cardiac resuscitation was carried out in the departments of the first and second therapy of the Samarkand branch of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care.

Based on the purpose of the study, the anamnesis of patients, the age of patients based on the data of the medical history, the examination was

conducted in two comparative groups. The first (main) group consisted of 5 patients under the age of 50 (1 woman; 4 men 66.66%) and 30 patients (11 women and 19 men) aged 50 years and older. The second (control) group consisted of 7 patients (2 women; 5 men) under the age of 50 years and 28 patients (9 women and 19 men) aged 50 years and older. The main group included 35 patients whose myocardial infarction had not appeared 6 hours after diagnosis, with an average age of 57 years, while the majority of patients in the group were men-23 (65.7%) and women-12 (34.3%). The main group included 35 patients whose myocardial infarction still persisted for 6 hours after diagnosis, with an average age of 60.5 years, while the majority of patients in the group were men-24 (68.6%) and women-9 (31.4%).

Results of the study: In the first group, clinical, functional and laboratory studies showed that the first (I) 3 out of 35 patients in the period from the onset of the disease to the first 12 hours, another 8.57% redevelop myocardial infarction. Patients with acute circulatory disorders of varying degrees and manifestations in the brain in the first hours of admission to the hospital were observed in 2 (5.7%) patients. The proportion of smokers in group 1 is 18 people (51.4%). When acute circulatory insufficiency was detected in all admitted patients in group I, there were 6 (17.1%) with Killip Class I, 14 (40.0%) with Killip Class II, 12 (34.3%) with Killip Class III, 2 (5.7%) with Killip Class IV. In the hospital, according to the standard procedure, an ECG was performed immediately in patients, while in 22.3% of cases various rhythm and conduction disturbances were detected and eliminated. According to the results of laboratory studies, cases of hypercholesterolemia of varying severity were observed in 22 (68.9%) patients. When studying the ECG results, 14.3% (N-5) of myocardial infarctions with anterior wall lesion, 27.7% (N-9) with anterior side wall lesion, 17.1 (N-6) with side wall lesion, 28.6% (N-10) with posterior wall lesion were identified.

In the second group, clinical, functional and laboratory studies have shown that in the second group (II) - 5 out of 35 patients in the period from the onset of the disease to the first 12 hours, another 14.3% redevelop myocardial infarction. Patients with acute circulatory disorders of varying degrees and manifestations in the brain in the first hours of admission to the hospital were observed in 3 (8.57%) patients. The proportion of smokers in group 2 is 15 people (42.9%). When acute circulatory insufficiency was detected in all admitted patients in group I, there were 2 (5.7%) with Killip class I, 14 (40.0%) with Killip class II, 15 (42.9%) with Killip class III, 4 (11.4%) with Killip Class IV. In the hospital, according to the standard, an ECG was performed dynamically in patients, while in 51.4% of cases various rhythm and conduction disturbances were detected and eliminated. According to the

results of laboratory studies, cases of hypercholesterolemia of varying severity were observed in 16 (74.3%) patients. The study of ECG analyses revealed 17.1% (N-6) of myocardial infarctions with anterior wall lesion, 22.9% (N-8) with anterior side wall lesion, 34.3 (N-12) with side wall lesion, 27.7% (N-9) with posterior wall lesion.

At the stages of the study, Echocardiography was used to evaluate cardiac activity in all patients and determine the hemodynamic status. A comparative analysis of cardiac activity and hemodynamics in the study groups showed certain modification in the heart. In patients of both the groups, enlargement of the left atrium (LP) and left ventricle (LV), the

posterior wall of the left ventricle, an increase in the thickness of the interventricular septum was detected. At the same time, changes in blood pressure in the left ventricle and pulmonary artery were observed in patients with chronic heart failure. These changes are related to the severity of MI. The results of Echocardiography complement the previous methods of laboratory and functional studies and represent the distribution of patients by functional class of chronic heart failure, as well as by severity associated with the presence of pulmonary hypertension. Table 1 shows the main echocardiographic indicators of patients in the group.

Table 1

Comparative analysis of hemodynamic parameters

Indicators	1 – Group (35)	2 – Group (35)	P
LV DE cm	5,7 [5,4-5,9]	5,4 [5,0-5,9]	< 0,05
LV SE cm	4,3 [3,6-5,25]	4,0 [3,7-4,3]	< 0,05
LV EF%	45,25 [39,5-52,0]	42 [38,0-54,0]	< 0,05
During Systolic PWLV cm	1,1 [1,0-1,2]	1,2 [1,1-1,3]	< 0,05
IVS cm	1,1 [1,0-1,2]	1,2 [1,1-1,3]	< 0,05
LA	4,5 [4,0-5,0]	4,5 [3,8-5,2]	< 0,05
RV	3,1 [2,9-3,3]	3,0 [2,9-3,1]	< 0,05
RA	4,4 [4,1-4,7]	4,3 [4,0-4,6]	< 0,05
PA pressure	24,9 [19,6-28,1]	22,0 [18,0-27,0]	< 0,05

Patients of both the groups showed a negative reaction to the bronchodilation test. Relative adverse changes were observed in patients of group 1 during echocardiography examination, in patients of both these groups it is associated with an exacerbation of MI.

The importance of the problem of MI treatment is determined by the high prevalence, high mortality, persistent disability of patients and deterioration in the quality of life. Coronary thrombosis plays a major role in the pathogenesis of acute myocardial infarction. In the treatment of AMI, measures aimed at faster restoration of the permeability of the damaged artery, as well as at combating reclusion, are crucial. Therefore, at present, the use of thrombolytic drugs is considered as one of the main therapeutic approaches to restore coronary blood flow. Currently the following types of thrombolytic drugs are widely used in the world: streptokinase, prourokinase, urokinase are the most common thrombolytic drugs.

Streptokinase is a protein derived from hemolytic streptococcus group C. The mechanism of action of this protein is the formation of an

equimolar complex with plasminogen. After that, as a result of internal transformations, an active center opens in the plasminogen molecule, and the streptokinase-plasminogen complex acquires the ability to activate plasminogen into plasma, which splits the fibrin of the thrombus into smaller fragments. Plasmin fragments reduce not only fibrin, but also fibrinogen circulating in the blood against the background of thrombolysis.

The results of the study showed that systemic thrombolytic therapy (TLT) in the early stages of MI had significant improvement in the results when using streptokinase.

It should be noted that in the group of patients with early MI during the first 12 hours, treatment was effective in 80% (p<0.05), since thrombolytic therapy was used in most patients. The treatment proved effective in 45% the patients admitted to the hospital in the end stages of the disease (more than 12 hours from the onset of the disease). It is observed that early hospitalization of patients is of high importance, thereby preventing disability and death of the patient.

Figure 1. Effectiveness of treatment

We know that every day spent by patients in the hospital significantly increases the cost of treatment. The TLT has made it possible to significantly reduce the length of stay of patients in the hospital (on average by 5-6 days). In addition, the duration of stay of patients in the intensive care unit is reduced, thereby freeing up space for other patients in need of medical care.

TLT had a complex positive effect on the course of the disease, leading to a reduction in deaths and prevention of complications such as

post-infarction aneurysms, preservation of functionally active myocardium, reduction of post-infarction remodeling of the heart, reduction of stress-induced myocardial ischemia, and achievement of reduction of arrhythmic complications of AMI. The frequency of post infarction aneurysms was minimal in patients with TLT (p-1 3.5%), significantly higher in patients without TLT (p-3 8.6%).

Figure 2. Frequency of post infarction aneurysms

Reliable evidence has been obtained that TLT in AMI significantly reduces the electrical instability of the atria and ventricles. The incidence of ventricular extra systoles and supraventricular extra systoles after TLT decreased by (N-4) 11.4% and (N-8) 22.8%,

respectively (p <0.05). Regarding the frequency of attacks of fluttering and ventricular fibrillation, a more pronounced dynamics was noted: in the groups of patients who underwent TLT, the frequency of such cardiac arrhythmias (n-13) decreased by 37% (P <0.01).

Figure 3. The frequency of arrhythmias after the use of TLT

An essential component of the treatment of patients with AMI is antiplatelet therapy. For a single oral administration, acetylsalicylic acid

(aspirin) was used, which was prescribed in an amount of 160-325 mg. From the second day, 75-160 mg is taken orally 1 time a day for a long

time.

Direct-acting anticoagulants in AMI were used to increase the effectiveness of thrombolytic therapy, to prevent repeated occlusion of the coronary artery, and to prevent thromboembolic complications. Heparin is administered intravenously at 60 units / kg (up to 4000 units), infusion-drip at 12 units / kg / h for 1-2 days. Then the dosage is determined depending on the APTT (APTT can be 1.5-2 times higher than normal). Control of APTT is not required when prescribing low-molecular-weight heparins. Fraxiparin (nadroparin calcium) ED 2850 anti-Ha p / k (0.3 ml) is administered 1 time a day or Kleksan (enoxaparin sodium) ED 4000 anti-Ha p / k (40 mg) is administered 1 time per day. Treatment with beta adreno blockers it is used in all patients with MI, unless there are contraindications. Contraindications include bradycardia (a decrease in heart rate to 50 per minute), a decrease in systolic blood pressure less than 90 mmHg, severe left ventricular insufficiency, signs of peripheral hypo perfusion, atrioventricular blockade, bronchial asthma or chronic obstructive upper respiratory tract disease according to anamnesis. Atenolol is prescribed 2.5-5 mg intravenously for the first time, with good tolerability - again with an interval of 10 minutes, it is done 2 times a day, then after a 15-minute interval, 50 mg is prescribed, after which they switch to 100 mg per day. Metoprolol is first administered intravenously at a dose of 2.5-5 mg bolus, and with good tolerability - repeatedly every 2-5 minutes until the total amount of 15 mg is reached from 4 mg to 2 times a later it is continued for 100 mg 2 times a day. Propranolol (anaprilin, inside) 2-3 mg intravenously bolus, with good tolerability - from 1 mg every 2

minutes to 0.1 mg / kg, up to a total dose of 80 mg 3 times a day after 2-3 days. ACE inhibitors (perindopril, Ramipril) were prescribed to patients with THEM from the first day of the disease with heart failure, low ejection fraction, large myocardial lesion and, in general, there were no contraindications to their use.

Nitrates are prescribed for persistent or recurrent stable myocardial ischemia, in acute cases of heart failure, with stable hypertension. Nitroglycerin (perlinganite) or isoket 5-10 mcg / min are administered drop by drop within 1-2 days from the first intake. It is not considered effective to prescribe nitroglycerines to all patients with MI.

Conclusion: Currently, acute myocardial infarction is a disease with high mortality, therefore it is a serious medical and social problem. Mortality rate after cardiogenic shock is highest in patients over 50 years of age. The main treatment of this disease is to prevent its progression, increase the resistance of patients to physical exertion and, consequently, improve the quality of life and prevents the exacerbation and development of the disease in the long term, reduce mortality. According to the results of the study, there were no significant differences in the occurrence of the frequency of side effects, but the use of effective treatment methods reduced the risk of developing MI, which increased the number of hospital appointment. Thus, the level of new research and the formation of new clinical recommendations in modern clinical practice are very high. Since in most cases there are no strict and clear recommendations describing all possible aspects of the treatment of such patients, it is necessary to constantly assess the risks and look out for new treatment options for patients.

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Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
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